

UNISECO

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Supporting the development of an agro-ecological market through Measure 16.2 of the Rural Development Program (RDP) in Navarra (Spain)

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Understanding and Improving the Sustainability of Agro-ecological Farming Systems in the EU

POLICY BRIEF

In Navarra, small-sized agro-ecological farmers have reached a good performance in environmentally friendly agricultural practices, but they are fragile on a social and economic level due to the lack of development of the agro-ecological market. In particular, small-sized farmers have problems to carry out processing and marketing of products individually.

RESEARCH FINDINGS

Through a participatory research approach, we found that in recent years the Navarra Government has financed three pilot projects through RDP Measure 16.2 in order to solve the processing and marketing problems of the small-sized agro-ecological farmers: Ekomercado, a monthly market for organic and local products; Ekoalde, a collection and sales center through which small organic producers distribute their products; and a group of 15 organic cereal farmers who share infrastructure and machinery.

The design of these projects was carried out in cooperation with the producers themselves, who are the ones who present their proposals to the Administration.

Participation of the public company INTIA as advisory service and catalyst of the projects was also remarkable. Producers, consultants and administration are thus forming a "Learning Community" to search for solutions.

All the stakeholders in the area of study considered these type of projects necessary, urgent and priority and highlighted them as one of the key strategies that enable the transition to agro-ecology.

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Country:
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Related to UNISECO case study:

Agro-ecological farming systems in Navarra & the Basque Country
<https://uniseco-project.eu/case-study/spain>

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Ekoalde, collection and sale centre for small-sized organic farmers

POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

In regions where the agro-ecological market is fragmented and underdeveloped, Administrations can make use of Measure 16.2 available in the RDP to finance pilot projects that seek to develop the agro-ecological market, by grouping small-sized producers to share services, machinery and infrastructures. Thanks to these policy measures, producers can access to infrastructure and machinery that would otherwise be unfeasible.

The innovative component is essential in these projects; only proposals that provide innovative solutions to problems identified by the sector should be financed.

Finally, the main objective of these policy measures must be to promote that these projects become profitable business initiatives, which do not depend on public aid.

FURTHER INFORMATION

Webpage of INTIA: <https://www.intiasa.es/es/>

Webpage of farmers association EHKolektiboa: <https://ehkolektiboa.eus/>

Webpages of projects financed by RDP Measure 16.2 in Navarra:

<https://www.ekoalde.org/es/>; <https://ekomercado.org/>

Agro-ecological farming systems in Navarra and the Basque Country (Story Map):

<https://uniseco-project.eu/case-study/spain>

ABOUT UNISECO:

UNISECO is a European research project aiming to develop innovative approaches to enhance the understanding of socio-economic and policy drivers and barriers for further development and implementation of agro-ecological practices in EU farming systems.

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<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/773901>

<https://zenodo.org/communities/uniseco-h2020/>

UNISECO in the EIP-Agri projects database:

<https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/find-connect/projects/understanding-and-improving-sustainability-agro>

VISIT THE UNISECO AGRO-ECOLOGICAL KNOWLEDGE HUB: <https://uniseco-project.eu>

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